

Short Communication

OF AFTER

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Abstract

Look before you leap is a great saying regarding after. It is a caution towards life. It alerts a person to think for after effect i.e., future consequences and complications of anything done. It advises to take precaution before doing anything. It is a polite request to a near and dear one.

Key words: After, later, afterwards

Introduction

Creative writing is based more on manifestation rather than on expression. It does not inform, rather it reveals. So it bears no reference. The best creative writing is critical, and the best critical writing is creative. This article is an outcome of thinking about creative writing meant for a general readership. As such, I have adopted a free style methodology so that everyone can enjoy the pleasure of reading. As you might know, Francis Bacon (1561-1626), the immortal essayist, wrote many essays namely 'Of Love', 'Of Friendship', 'Of Ambition', 'Of Studies', and so on. The multiple-minded genius correctly pointed out that all the words of the dictionary can be used as themes for essays. But little has been done since his death to continue or finish his monumental task. Bacon's unique individual style of presentation ignited my imagination and encouraged me to write creative essays as a method of relieving a wide range of emotions through catharsis.

ARTICLE

After means following in time, place, or order. For example: Let's walk after dinner.

It implies later than someone or something else.

After is a daily drama. Man faces it. He has to face it. He is bound to face it. Thus man, willy-nilly, experiences after, from cradle to coffin, in various ways in its various forms and features having different degrees and dimensions as well viz., the day after tomorrow, well after, soon after, a quarter after, day after day, week after week, life after death, etc.

A judicious person knows well that if the arrow is thrown from the bow then it cannot be made return back. Similarly, in argument one must mind the usage of words thus uttered. If any filthy language is used or any vulgar gesture is shown then the situation becomes critical and afterwards it cannot be made up or managed easily. Then the focus will be diverted in any irrelevant direction causing ultimately frustration of the target objective. After implies future. In selecting business and life partner after has immense effect. If the business partner is not good then the firm is collapsed and the less intelligent partner is imposed by debt instead of profit. Sometimes the innocent partner commits suicide to escape from ill-fame or shame or both simultaneously.

In case of marriage partner after has serious impact. If matching is not

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considered seriously and properly but ignored to judge it after then the marriage relation cannot be successful. Marriage is a long journey. Tolerance is its only fuel. If matching is not good then both the partners cannot tolerate each other. Both blame both. Both disbelief both. Ultimately, separation appears timely not after. In case of divorce if both are agreed then there lies no problem. If either of the partners impose condition or demand compensation then it starts an uncertain voyage.

Present implies temporary. It is for the time being only. After means future that does not and will not appear afterwards as it is now. An intelligent person knows it seldom a fool. So a judicious person thinks for the changed situation. He prepares accordingly. His strategy is, "Think for the best and prepares for the worst". It has double benefit. Best thinking implies optimism which is an asset in human life. It is a driving force for its positivity. It offers confidence which is virtual cash and sky is its limit. Preparation for worst enables a person to win the battle of uncertain future at ease for sound preparation. Similarly, treating is a strategy to kill the time and be prepared to win the war. Thus preparation implies after. Good preparation pays. Bad preparation pains. Here lies the uniqueness of after.

An intelligent person saves for the future. He deposits money in bank or any financial institution for his save guard i.e., to battle against the unknown future. Again someone invests in the share market. They say the return of share market is more than term or fixed deposit of the bank. But there is risk. Share market may sweep away all the money rendering the investor quite penniless in the twinkle of an eye. The share market investor says that no risk, no gain implies high risk, high gain.

Someone is afraid of taking any kind of risk little or much. So he deposits in the bank. Someone is ready to take any kind of risk. He does not like normal life. Routine life is quite tedious to him. It causes monotony which offers him agony. To him variety is the spice of life. He readily mixes those spices in his life to render it more palatable. He relishes it. He enjoys it. So he invests in the share market. Both are personality traits.

In share market someone loses all and some other gains all. Actually, a few persons control the market. They simply plunder the money of the whole population. A timid person sees both winner and loser. But he cannot think the fortune of the winner. He only thinks the misfortune of the loser. So he does not invest. In contrast the courageous person is entrepreneur in nature. He sees the winner. He ignores or overlooks the loser. He considers

the loser as less talented. Perseverance is a must in share market. It pays after in future. The loser lacks in perseverance. He dives in the ocean of share market having unfathomable depth. He gains in the long run.

An experienced person compares value of money between present and after i. e, future. He calculates the capacity of present money in future. He wants to know if one kilogram of meat, at present, costs 10 \$ then how much meat he will get in future say after five years spending 10\$. This depreciation of money and inflation are very crucial factors in the world of investment. Here unknown factors are more than known factors. The world is changing. Simultaneously the parameters are also changing. An investor becomes perplexed. Double change disables judgment causing loss ultimately in investment.

A good business man thinks for profit. A great business man thinks for loss. The later argues that profit is not the factor, rather loss is the factor. Profit means incoming. Loss means outgoing. Profit is within custody. Loss is out of custody and beyond control. The goer is not returner. Due to loss many novice business men are simply washed out from the business world. In initial stage they cannot perceive it. They experiences helpless condition later on when nothing can be done to compensate the deficiency. This is hard reality.

They say where goodness ends greatness begins.

A good business man knows when to purchase, from where to purchase, how much to purchase and from whom to purchase. He is not an expert about sell. Sale is the essence of business. It determines the Return on Investment i.e., ROI which is the only important thing in business. In contrast the great business man knows well when to sell, where to sell, how much to sell and whom to sell. He does not sell the total stock. He keeps some stock for future. He sales afterwards during crisis period and earns huge profit. Sometimes he cannot sell all the goods that became degraded. Then he allures the customers and sells the rest amount at a cheaper price stating stock clearance sale. The rest degraded goods he had to throw into the dustbin. Instead he earns money. As such they say so called goods of "stock clearance cell" lack in quality. Cheap has three phases. Ultimately, cheap is not cheap at all.

A cautious business man sells at a less profit than facing loss for the unsold goods. He contends that it is better to sell at a less profit than repent for higher profit in future. Future means uncertain. Unsold goods imply total loss. The proverb goes something is better than nothing. Similarly, some trade is better than no trade. These are the trade secrets. Very few business men know the password of this strategy. In fact business means forecast. Forecast implies after. Here lies the importance of after.

After sales service is very important of any rising start up entrepreneur for its mere existence in the present era of tough competition. But the ill-fame goes that after sales service is not available after sales. They are missing just with the sale.

Earlier the company would give guarantee of any product. At present guarantee has been replaced by warranty which is a modern management term. It is a modern tool to befool the consumers. The product works well during warranty period. But the most interesting point is that the product

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is so tuned that it goes out of order just with the warranty period is over. The most interesting point is that the cost of repairing is almost of a new product. Further, the company attracts the old customer with another tool viz., exchange offer. The old customer purchases a new one. The company is engaged in production. Thus the circuit is complete.

After means foresight. It means future thinking. Antonym of after is "Do it now" which means strike the iron when it is hot. The hot iron will be cold after some time. Then higher strike will be required to get the desired shape. Higher strike means higher cost coupled with higher effort. Afterwards it may be difficult to perform it and sometimes it may be impossible even.

After shock of earth quake is very dangerous. It continues for a longtime causing huge loss and destruction.

After means delay. It is a tool to harass someone who needs the service urgently. The harasser does it to squeeze money from the victim. The victim gives bribe or rather becomes bound to give money thinking future consequence. He thinks that it is cheaper to give bribe than repeated travelling expenditure. The business man considers bribe as speed money which the harasser glorifies as one time expenditure.

After is a tool of a lazy person. He always speaks of tomorrow whenever he is asked to do anything today. Further if he is asked to do anything tomorrow he readily speaks to do it day after tomorrow. His answer is always ready. That tomorrow never comes even after day after tomorrow. It is an infinite voyage of an uncertain destination. None knows when he will do it. It seems even he does not the day of his being active.

If someone does not do any assigned duty in time for any cause. Then he may face more causes to perform it later on. Since he cannot do due to fewer problems then surely he will not be able to do the job conquering more problems of future. Sometimes he may not be able to do it at all. A wise knows it except a fool.

Human life is the combination of various stages. Each facets of life is unique with defined duty. Childhood is for playing. Student life implies for study and so on. Student life is very crucial to build the career. If a student does not read attentively and leaves study to do it afterwards then he fails in the examination. Similarly, if a child is engaged to work then he becomes a child laborer.

Now, both unsuccessful student and child laborer are curse and headache as well as shame to any nation as well. Such a poor nation cannot see the ray of development easily. This is the outcome of after.

CONCLUSION

Look before you leap is a great saying regarding after. It is a caution towards life. It alerts a person to think for after effect i.e., future consequences and complications of anything done. It advises to take precaution before doing anything. It is a polite request to a near and dear one.

REFERENCES

No reference, since the present article is an outcome of Creative Nonfiction Writing.

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